

Electrochemical Reduction of 3-Hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavone on GCE in DMF Solution

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Flavonoid compounds have great significance in biological and pharmaceutical fields. Electrochemical studies of a number of flavonoid compounds have been made¹. It has been established² that in a wide range of pH, one polarographic wave of irreversible $2e^-$ reduction is obtained. However, the cyclic voltammetric study of the titled compound has not been reported so far. The present communication describes the study of electroreduction behaviour of 3-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavone (**1**) on GCE in 80% DMF solution and reduction potential is compared with that of 3-hydroxyflavone (**2**).

1; R₁ = OH, R₂ = OMe
2; R₁ = OH, R₂ = H

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows the typical cyclic voltammogram recorded for the reduction of compounds **1** and **2** of 1 mM concentration in 80% DMF at 75 mV s⁻¹ sweep rate. Well-defined single peak shaped voltammogram with no complementary anodic peak on reverse scan is observed. The cathode peak potential is found to shift towards more negative value with increasing sweep rate. E_p varies linearly with log v . No linear relationship is found for $t_p/\sqrt{v}$ with v , and $t_p/\sqrt{v}$ decreases with increasing v (Table 1). Hence there must be a chemical reaction coupled with the electrochemical process³ (probably a protonation), peak current is

found to increase with increase in concentration and peak potential is shifted to the anodic direction at constant sweep rate.

Fig. 1 Typical cyclic voltammograms recorded for the reduction of compounds **1** and **2** in 80% DMF, concn = 1 mM, sweep rate 75 mV s⁻¹

The course of the reaction was monitored by the and after electrolysis, solution was taken out and the product recovered from ether extract. The $2e^-$ reduction product was confirmed by its characteristic uv absorption maximum value (550 nm)¹ and specific colour reactions⁵.

The electrode process can be considered as the formation of a monoanion radical² by pre-electron addition followed by protonation of the ion-radical. Then the uptake of the second electron occurs with no further requirement of activation energy so that only a single peak is obtained (Scheme 1).

It is observed that when *o*-CH₃ group is present in a position conjugated with the carbonyl group, it decreases the ease of reduction which is reflected in a shift of the E_p value to more negative side.

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PEAK POTENTIAL VALUES FOR 1 AND 2

Compd. Concn. mM	Sweep rate mV s ⁻¹	E _p (mV)		i _p mA	i _p /√v mA/V s ⁻¹
		1	2		
1	0.020	1036	896	0.229 9	1.630
	0.050	1175	916	0.247 3	1.100
	0.075	1185	932	0.247 7	0.904
	0.200	1313	1002	0.248 2	0.555
2	0.020	825	710	0.207 1	1.468
	0.050	856	750	0.213 5	0.954
	0.075	858	752	0.253 1	0.924
	0.200	907	806	0.335 4	0.750

Experimental

Cyclic voltammetric measurements were carried

out with a BAS-100 electrochemical analyser. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. All potentials were measured with reference to SCE at 298 ± 1 K and the counter electrode used was platinum wire. The glassy carbon disc (5 mm dia) was embedded in teflon gasket with provision for electrical connections. It was polished with 1/0 to 4/0 emery papers successively.

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